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JIS

Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS)

Vision

“ENRICHING BEAUTIFUL MINDS TOWARDS INTELLIGENT MINDS”

The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) aims to disseminate scholarly research articles and papers to the wider community with the aim of offering an academic and scientific platform that provides an outlet to authors. The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) is an open access online journal. Initially, the JIS will provide an online version, but is planning a print version later in this academic journey. The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) focuses on a high-quality academic research articles and papers. All categories of research are of interest to the JIS, including insightful empirical studies, conceptual papers, commentary, essays, and theoretical articles.

JIS is an interdisciplinary platform and invites authors, academics, students, researchers, leaders, managers, scientists for their contributions in the disciplines of sciences, sociology, education, philosophy, humanities and management. Articles and Papers of scientific and academic rigour in Qualitative, Quantitative, Mixed or Blend methods are welcome.

JIS intends to publish two issues per annum (May and November).

Submissions to, and Publication in, the JIS is free.

All papers submitted for publication will be peer reviewed.

Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS)

mission is to “Guide Beautiful Minds towards Intellectual Enrichment”

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Editorial

Dear Readers,

We are delighted to announce the publication of our November 2025 issue. This marks yet another significant achievement for the journal.

In Volume 9, Issue 2, November 2025, we feature engaging articles on various interdisciplinary topics, making it easier for readers to find a diverse range of articles on one platform. These articles will also be uploaded to DOAJ and other scientific indexes.

Our next volume for 2026 will be published in May 2026; we invite authors to submit their scientific articles.

Submission to JIS is open to authors from all disciplines. We look forward to increased participation to help Enrich the Beautiful Minds toward Developing Intelligent Minds.

Thank you very much.

Let us join and collaborate together to **ENRICH the BEAUTIFUL MINDS
TOWARDS INTELLIGENT MINDS**

Mani Man Singh Rajbhandari. Ph.D.
Founder and Editor-in-Chief
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